

Terrorism in The Name of Religion Has Become Predominant Model in the Modern World.

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Through the long historical of humanity, interaction between religion and terrorism has unbreakable linkage. The term of “New Terrorism” is defined in General Assembly Summit of United Nation in 1994; many innocent people continue to lose their lives, because the increasing of terrorist discriminations in the world. Islam is used by terrorist leaderships to change innocent people’s thinking to be the terrorist by using belief in religion. In last two decades the terrorist attacks were responsible by Islamic terrorist group, which based in Middle East region, including Al-Qaeda, Taleban and Islamic state (ISIS), Buku Haram in Africa etc. We would not accuse that, Islam creates terrorism, but Islam is mainly using to serve the nationalism of some Islamic countries and its political advantages.

Therefore, the discussion bellow aimed to examine the sources of terrorism, instruments and the international response to contain the spreading of terrorism. We used the evidences of criminal case, the governmental reports, journals and books which issued on terrorism to support our arguments in this analysis.

Keywords: RELIGION, ISLAM, RELIGIOUS MOTIVATION, AL-QAEDA/ ISLAMIC STATE (ISIS)/TALEBAN/BUKU HARAM, REVOLUTION

Introduction

The religious and political violence are linked for long history, but it has changed characteristics in its vision during the modern world. Acts of violence perpetrated in the name of religion have been reported with great prominence in recent times, particularly in the opening years of the 21st century, due to the association, whether suspected or confirmed that these acts frequently have with Islam.¹ Since the terrorist attack in 11 September 2001, some scholars has linked this extremely disillusioned violence to religious doctrine, due this criminal attacking considered as motivate encouragement by religious in term of “religious terrorism”, in particular

¹ Peter Kuti, *Terror in the Name of God: Confronting Acts of Religious Violence in Liberal Society*, the Centre for Independent Studies: Religious and Civil Society, Introduction: When People of Faith Turn to Violence, P.7.

“Islamic terrorism”, to new heights. We remember that, few day after attacking of the World Trade Center in New York, United State, Al-Qaeda group which led by Islamic leadership, they released a media by claiming in responsibility to this terrorist attack. In the modern world, only Islamic is remained as a main actor in criminal discrimination activities, by the witness of many main Islamic terrorist groups in terrorism world as well as Taliban and Al-Gaeda in Afghanistan, Islam State (ISIS), Buku Haram in Nigeria and Abu Sayyaf in Philippine. They used extremely belief in Islam ideology to motivate the terrorist; even mission purpose in practice is not benefit for religious nom, but surely, it’s all for political advantages by counter the legal government-state strategy or group interest. Through debating, the terrorist attacked purpose in this new century becomes really complicated. In term of “religious terrorism” mean, religious plays very important role as “mission from god” encourage terrorist to commit the crime against humanity. Terrorism is defined as political violence which is designed to kill the mass of people, even civilian is main target, to exploit the media for achieving maximum attainable publicity, to influence the targeted audience, and to reach political goals or desired long-term end states. Based on United State code, they defined terrorism as: “Premeditated, politically motivated violence perpetrated against noncombatant targets by subnational groups or clandestine agents, usually intended to influence an audience”.² In addition, the term of “Religious Terrorism” is frequently used in the context of a broader set of claims about the nature and causes of such acts of violence and the groups and movements who perpetrate them. This topic is now ubiquitous in public debate among scholar and researcher, the popular media and academic scholarship, especially in the fields of terrorism studies and international relations (IR). Sometimes, it’s not easily to define the religious terrorism or political violence; even they have same political commitment.

Therefore, this paper claims to discuss on the reason why the religious effective influence is used in terrorist leaderships, how does the effective of its doctrine in motivations and how its images to Islam, the second largest religious in the world. However, Terrorism in the name of religion has surely become the predominant model in the modern world.

Materials and methods

1. Interaction between terrorism and Islam

Since the serine attack in Metro station at Tokyo, Japan in 1994 and terrorist attack the World Trade Center at 11 September 2011, Islamic terrorism is rising and influenced to the world security. The Islamic terrorism has spread to some parts of the world, as the case of terrorism threats in Nigeria and central Africa. The Islamist sect known as Boko Haram, has carried out numerous acts of violence; the group abducted hundreds of school children in April 2014 and has killed more than 13,000 civilians over the past five years.³ Surely to say that, the quickly spreading to terrorism, is threatening to the global security, and reasoned to create the

² United Code, Tittle 22: Foreign Relation and Intercourse, Chapter 38: Department of State, *Terrorism*.

³ Antonios Kouroutakis, *Islamic Terrorism: the Legal Impact on the Freedom of Religion in the United State and Europe*, Free University of Berlin, 26 Nov 2015, P.135.

international cooperation among states and blocks to counter terrorist attack. In same manner, Islamic terrorism, Islamist terrorism and radical Islamic terrorism has been defined by some scholar or international organization that has duty to design political principle to against the terrorism. They considered most of terrorist attacks came from Islamic leaderships. This criminal activity is set by campaign or doctrine committed by image of groups or individuals who professional in Islamic ideology or Islamist motivations. Exactly, Islamic terrorist leadership has justified their violent tactics through the interpretation of Quran, based on their own political ambitions or intentions and goals. The idea of Islamic supremacy is set in most of Muslims perception and encapsulated in the formula. The Muslim believed that Islam is exalted and have nothing is exalted or better than its ideology.

The terminology of the type of “new terrorism” has greatly gained in prominence and without doubt has become a central issue throughout the world.⁴ The terminology of “new terrorist” is defined because of its complicated purpose. Both of the old or new terrorism are not much change its characteristics, particularly motivation of terrorist. Because of Al Qaeda and the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS), are considered the world terrorist organization. Also, they are Muslims, and their headquarters also base in region of Middle East countries (Arabic Country). Response such issue, Terrorism usually listed to agenda of United Nation and Regional Organization. After United State attacked Taliban in Afghanistan in 2011 and invaded to Iraq in 2013, this concern becomes more complicated, both millions of innocent Muslim and militia group were under attacks. Additionally, the extent to which such antiterrorism policies have been ultra vires and have disproportionally affected Muslim citizens and immigrants is still under scrutiny.⁵ Presently, security issues have become a priority for the United and European Union (EU) if compare to other part of the world. Through nationalism, Islam is playing as unbreakable linkage of religion and terrorism.

To give strongly support to arguments of the interaction between terrorism and Islam, the evidences of this linkage should be raised as well as the causes of terrorism studies: how terrorist group leadership uses religion, the Iranian revolution to take monarchy out the power, the suicide terrorism cause of belief motivation and related cases. The reason of social and political injustice in some states also became main cause to change a normal civilian to a terrorist. The pain and suffering by war long time, when they are trying to right what they perceive to be a social or political or historical wrong, they has been stripped of their land or rights, or denied these, particularly strongly lacking of economic opportunity, losing of ethnic identity or sovereignty intervention, they would decide to make some political movement or any nationalist activities to show their opposition voice to the world. Those movements could be peace movement or violence. A long with this, sometime the group of identity also choose terrorism, to demand their fundamental needs as well as economic and political interest and integrate to be legal party of state, religious hegemon or independent so far.

⁴ Alexander Spenser, Article: *Questioning the Concept of “New Terroism”*: Peace, Conflict and Development, 8 Jan 2016, P.4. www.peacestudiesjournal.org.uk

⁵ Peter Tarlow, *the Interaction of Religion and Terrorism*, International Journal of Safety and Security of Tourism/Hospitality, P.13. North American Academic Research, 4(4) | April 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4672479> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 45

In other hand, because of the belief that violence or its threat will be effective way, and usher in change. Another way of saying this is the belief that violent means justify the ends. Many terrorists in history said sincerely that they chose violence after long deliberation, because they felt they had no choice. In practice, we can see the main terrorist groups in the world as we know, Taliban and Al-Gaeda in Afghanistan, Islam State (ISIS), Buku Haram and Abu Sayyaf in Philippine. The question must be raised, in order to succeed their political purpose, how can they motivate or persuade people to join their movement is. Answer in practice is, religious is used, mainly Islam. So, no doubt that, most of people around the world, are feeling race sometimes to Muslim even in travelling or social gathering. However, religion has also caused great acts to occur, and it has acted as a social control mechanism for millions of people. There is an old rabbinic tale that teaches us that God gave us the “Ten Commandments” not for some great religious or philosophical reason but merely for one reason and one reason alone: we needed them. That is to say, human beings needed a social road map if societies were to exist.⁶ Because of some Muslims became innocent people of war in regions, Islam is strongly effective strategy to use.

The case of Iranian revolution in 1979, anti-government group led by Khomeini, an Islamic leader used religious ideology to make the peace demonstration and political movements against westernization and American influences in Iran. It means, religion not only use for terrorist attack but also serve for nationalism among other states. They argued that, the wave of terrorism has Islam at its heart. It began in 1979 when three events occurred: The Iranian Revolution, the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan and a new Islamic century began.⁷ Iran is very conservative society and extremely Islamic stats in region. Their leader used nationalism of Islam hegemony and culture for national perspective. Islam ideology became main doctrine for revolte tactic. By historical background, this Islamic revolution in Iran was created in order to take the monarchy of Mohammad Reza Shah Pahlavi from rolling state power, and replace by conservative Islamism and Khomeini leadership rather than with another leader, civilization and western ideology. In addition, It is credited in part to the spread of the Shia version of the Islamic revival that opposed Westernization and saw Ayatollah Khomeini as following in the footsteps of the Shi'a Imam Husayn ibn Ali and the Shah in the role of Husayn's foe, the hated tyrant Yazid I.⁸ It showed the strongly influence of Islamic ideology in political affairs of state. As the result, who is trust on Islamic leadership, though that their civilization would decline and replaced by the western model, that caused thousands of Iranian students joint the demonstration. However, sometimes they would crackdown by pro-monarchy forces, and violence confrontation. So, Iranian revolution was successfully by using Islamic nationalism.

Furthermore, the extremely belief on religious also influence to change the follower perception and characteristics. They can do everything for their belief even sacrifice their own life. Robert Paper provided

⁶ Peter Tarlow, *the Interaction of Religion and Terrorism*, International Journal of Safety and Security of Tourism/Hospitality, P.3.

⁷ Erik Manik, *Terrorism: Its Past, Present and Future Prospect*, State of the Union, 2007, P.157.

⁸ Erik Manik, *Terrorism: Its Past, Present and Future Prospect*, State of the Union, 2007, P.157.

argument that, the strength of terrorists' commitment to cause destruction is underlined by the terrorists' willingness to sacrifice their own lives in the process.⁹ He has studied some case of how extremely belief persuades them to commit the crime. Some terrorist attacks were happen in Middle East or in France; were suicide terrorism or suicide boomer. We can assume that, religion gives influence terrorism in strongly effectiveness. Paper and scholars else, have strongly supported to such argument. The great destructive of terrorism gives message alerting to any government and state, to high concentrate and urgently response this issue on time. The law on freedom of religion might be re-check and amendment by some states. This religious terrorism has given prominence to suicide terrorism, and it witnessed to cause of chemical terrorist attack at Metro station (Tokyo), in 1993. Backward to 1983, the terrorist organization of Hezebollar of Shia who supported by Iran, carried out massive suicide terrorist attack the United State marines and French paratroopers in Lebanon, in order to against the western influence to Middle East. As we known Iran is extremely Islamic state, they used hegemony of religion to link with their nationalism being tactics to engage with world affairs as a game of power ambition in region, and showed about opposite perspective of westernization. Based on some cases above, we have no doubt that why terrorist group leadership has chosen belief motivation in religion to reach their political commitments, because, exist beliefs and most effectiveness strategy. At last, these attacks resulted in serious casualties and strongly influenced the respective governments to design counter terrorism policy and building up national security to ensure safety for their people.

However, some scholars claimed the Islam has contributed as cause of terrorism. If we understand clearly about religion destination, its vision is to promote peace and happiness among all humanity, even different status, social classification and colors. By the witness, Amy Zalman absolutely has rejected the idea of a root cause linkage between religion and terrorism stating: "Although many people today believe that religious fanaticism "causes" terrorism, it isn't true".¹⁰ It is absolutely true, if we focus on the religion vision and destination. But in other part of reality of human historical page, the religious ideology is not the cause or encouragement to terrorism, because there are many religious fanatics who do not choose terrorism or any form of violence to succeed their vision. But the religious fanaticism also benefits to create conditions that are favorable for terrorism, by using extremely belief or nationalism. So, there must also be other conditions that in combination provoke some people to see terrorism as an effective way of creating change in their world".¹¹ The political assumption behind terrorism has been always used to explain as main course of civil war or internal problem in Islamic states at Middle East. Sometimes, religion is also given as the reason of conflicts among state and state as well as between Arabic state and Israel, the internal crisis in Iraq, the rise of the Islamic State (ISIS), the Iraq-Iran divide, the Christian-Muslim problems in Lebanon, and Egypt, and the

⁹ Erik Manik, *Terrorism: Its Past, Present and Future Prospect*, State of the Union, 2007, P.161.

¹⁰ Peter Tarlow, *the Interaction of Religion and Terrorism*, International Journal of Safety and Security of Tourism/Hospitality, P.13.

¹¹ Amy Zalman, *The Causes of Terrorism*, September 30, 2016.

internal strife in Libya. Those problems have given the opportunity to super power to intervention, in influence to its region of Middle East.

In shortly assumption, after cold war terrorism becomes new world war. It is dangerous and threatening to global security. Nowadays, terrorist movement is influencing and spreading to all areas in the world. The growing of technological system also provides opportunity to terrorist groups on promoting their criminal discrimination. We cannot ignore this point, based on their network building. Simultaneously, al-Qaeda has evolved into a movement that operates in over 70 countries and is present in the cyberspace. It has survived attempts to destroy it by military means and adapted to a new situation. It has been able to extend its influence to Muslim communities in European countries.¹² In additionally, according to data of the Global Terrorism Database, over 180,000 terrorist attacks including information on more than 88,000 bombings, 19,000 assassinations, and 11,000 kidnappings since 1970.¹³ This numbers were showed on the public Medias. But we still don't know exactly data which were happen in all areas, beside the official recording by government and any international organizations. Therefore, based on this number, all governments should arm to strengthen national security and build cooperation in bilateral or multilateral framework, to combat with terrorism.

2. The world response to terrorism

In recent decades, the terrorism becomes more complicated. Complicated because, many actors are getting involved to do terrorist attack preparation. It not only terrorist group known as non-state actor, but also the state sponsor and state terrorism are staying in part of terrorism. It difficult to define and decline terrorism spreading, while some legal governments are suspected as a main supporter behind, even financial and weapon equipment. In political manner, sometime terrorist group is just puppet of the state, is used to serve its political benefit. The growing of recognition that “war on terror” is not just a physical confrontation, but rather a struggle of ideas and mindsets, has been reflected in the 2006 National Security Strategy of the United States of America.¹⁴ Since increasingly of Islamic terrorist attacks, through bilateral and multilateral cooperation among stats and United Nation mechanisms were promoting.

Under United Nation umbrella, all member states raised the terrorism concern during its general assembly summit. As we remembered in 1994, the UN had discussed and defined the term of “Terrorism”. But waiting until 8 September 2006, the General Assembly had adopted the global counter terrorism strategy. It is the only one unique of international instrument to enhance national, regional and international security, and the effort to act against the terrorism threats in multilateral framework. Through its adoption that all Member States have agreed the first time to a common strategic and operational approach to fight terrorism, not only sending a clear message that terrorism is unacceptable in all its forms and manifestation but also resolving to take

¹² Erik Manik, *Terrorism: Its Past, Present and Future Prospect*, State of the Union, 2007, P.169.

¹³ <https://www.start.umd.edu/gtd/about/homepage>.

¹⁴ Erik Manik, *Terrorism: Its Past, Present and Future Prospect*, State of the Union, 2007, P.167.

practical steps individually and collectively to prevent and combat it. Those practical steps include a wide array of measures ranging from strengthening state capacity to counter terrorist threats to better coordinating United Nations system's counter-terrorism activities.¹⁵ To practice of counter terrorism strategy in effectiveness, UN had provide the four main doctrines for state members to practice and respect, such as addressing the condition conducive to the spread of terrorism, preventing and combating terrorism, building state capacity and strengthening the role of UN and ensuring human right and the role of law.

In case of the United State and European countries, the governments have created the policy to counter-terrorism, by tightening national security, reforming the immigration policy and concentrate on the governing of religious freedom and Islamic people who immigrate to live in that region. Remembered event, United State and alliances also used military forces to battle with the terrorist militia group directly, the attacking to Afghanistan in 2001 and invasion to Iraq in 2003. The impact of Islamic terrorism after the September 11 attacks became scaring and threats to the whole regional security. Undoubtedly, the terrorist attacks of 9/11 and the events that followed in Europe accelerated the adoption of stricter antiterrorism legislation in Europe and in the United States, as the correlation between Islamic terrorism and immigration was brought to the surface.¹⁶ Also, Looking to a number criminal cases of Islamic terrorism at the post-September 11 and after in the United State, they were increasingly in comparison by federal and state courts and the European Court of Human Rights. This case caused them to push the limitations on Muslims' religious freedoms and the demonstrated favoritism towards existing religious majorities. As evidence, the French Parliament also banned the wearing of the Islamic full, head-and-body veil in public places, colloquially known as the "burqa ban," in 2010.¹⁷

In other hand United State and European are also working closely with local governments in Middle East to decline the terrorism spreading and influence. Usually they are operating on battle in practice to occupy terrorist region and re-prepare its security. Since the 11 September attack, the counter-terrorism spending by Western countries has increased over the past 15 years. Since 2001, United States federal expenditure on homeland security has grown on average by \$360 billion annually. While it is not possible to calculate total EU's spending on the counter-terrorism with any precision, EU's spending is estimated to have increased from €5.7 million in 2002 to €93.5 million in 2009. The "Security and Citizenship" heading in the EU budget was slightly reduced, from €2 172 million in 2014 to €2 146.73 million in 2015.¹⁸ Such a willing to response on Islamic terrorist attack, should be encouraged, because those criminal discriminations are still happening increasingly.

¹⁵ *UN Global Counter Terrorism Strategy*, United Nations, adopted by Consensus, 2006.

¹⁶ Antonios Kouroutakis, *Islamic Terrorism: The Legal Impact on Freedom of Religion in the United State and Europe*, 2015, P.144.

¹⁷ Antonios Kouroutakis, 2015, P.136.

¹⁸ *Terrorism: the EU's Response*, European Parliament Research Service, European Parliament, 2015.

Conclusion

In the last decade, there are some incidents have occurred in the global scale considered as terrorism. It was affecting to international security and lost innocent lives, which not only Muslim-majority states in Africa and Asia, but also several other countries, with different region, color and model of ideology. Most of terrorist attacking were happening mostly in Middle East, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iraq and Syria where foreign militia bases and political influences, known as America and some of Western states. Beside, this region terrorist also spread and threat within the European Union, Australia, the United Kingdom and the South East Asia countries, such as Indonesia, Philippine and Thailand. Those countries in South East Asia also have terrorist militia base, which are network of international terrorist group, Taleban, Al-Qaeda and Islamic State (ISIS).

However, all religions have the same destiny to build peace, happiness and prosperity on earth. But Islam becomes unbreakable linkage between religion and terrorism. Because of their nationalism, suffering from historical background created by the western state and terrorism state or state sponsor strategy in Arabic region, no doubt that Islam gets engage directly to terrorism. Even though, such terrorist attacks have targeted not only deferent religious people but also Muslims and non-Muslims. In a number of the worst-affected Muslim-majority regions, are remained these terrorists have been met by armed, independent resistance groups, state actors and their proxies, and elsewhere by condemnation coming from prominent Islamic figures. In order to reach their political goal, those group leaderships not distracted to use existing belief as Islamic ideology to motivate members. Moreover, Islamic terrorist purpose also to fear the social perception by using the violence again mass of people. Through the context in which terrorist tactics are used is often a large-scale, unresolved political conflict. Some causes of the born of terrorism military, the historical events have recorded such as the secession of a territory to form a new sovereign state or become part of a different state, dominance of territory or resources by various ethnic groups, imposition of a particular form of government, economic deprivation of a population, opposition to a domestic government or occupying army (some terrorist boomer targeted to US and western military in Iraq and Afghanistan), and Religious fanaticism also.

Since the increasingly of terrorist attacks, terrorism issue also became agenda of any international institutions meeting particularly the summit in United Nation assembly in early of 1994. The next meetings respectively have been discussing to design and update strategy to combat with terrorism and defined the kind of relevance concerns. From the beginning, the war against terrorism has been both a battle of arms conflict and a battle of perception. The way to decline the spreading of terrorism, we need to fight against the terrorists in practice and against their murderous ideology in soft politic campaign. In attentively response some states have directly involve to war by using military force and other instruments of national power to kill or capture the terrorists, the example: the war declaration of United State to crackdown the government of Taleban and Al-Qaeda militia group in Afghanistan in 2001 and invasion to Iraq in 2003. They also created some principles to control

of any nation, the state was suspected as terrorism state and state sponsor, especially cut off their sources of support.

Additional point, in order to winning the war on terror means, we need to confrontation in the battle of ideas. Based on the discussion above, ideological philosophy and belief to Islamic religion are important factors to motivate Islamic terror. It means the ideas that can turn the disenchanted into murderers willing to kill innocent victims, seriously become suicide boomer. The same time of combating against terror, it becomes a battle of ideas. This strategy, does it mean all states need to battle in field of religions. Exactly, after the terrorist attacks since 11 September 2001, caused of suffering and long civil wars in the Middle East and the Muslim becomes seriously victim in the game of politic geographical competition among stats and terrorist militia groups (non-state actor). An ignorance point is, the terrorists has distort the idea of jihad or religious ideology into murder perception against those they regard as apostates or unbelievers or enemy, including the different religious groups such as Christians, Jews, Hindus, and Buddhism (terrorist attack against Buddhism monk in south of Thailand) and other religious traditions. Sometime, they also attack to the same group of all Muslims who disagree with nationalism and political philosophy.

In short, the transnational terrorists confronting us today exploit the proud religion of Islam to serve the vision of political violence, to establish the illegal militia force, by Islamic tradition and subversion denies difference political perception and religious freedom. Therefore, all government of states should have to increase truly intention to resolve the terrorism concerns by working together, to keep international security, peace and prosperity, even the bilateral and multilateral framework.

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